

NON LINEAR VIBRATION METHOD TO DETECT IMPERFECTLY CONTACT INTERFACES IN COMPOSITE BEAMS

F.AMERINI, E.BARBIERI, M.MEO, U. POLIMENO

Material Research Centre, Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, The University of Bath, Bath, UK

SUMMARY

This paper presents a experimental campaign aimed at developing an integrity index, based on the observation of the nonlinear structural response of imperfect composite interfaces under free vibration, to measure the health state of contact interfaces in composite structures. The developed index was experimentally validated with promising results.

Keywords: vibration, nonlinear waves, non-perfect contact, harmonics, composite interfaces

ABSTRACT

Ultrasonic waves are useful tools to characterize the contact condition between composite components in non-destructive and noninvasive manners. It has been shown that the transmission and reflection coefficients of the ultrasonic wave are sensitive to the contact pressure or other contact parameters. Theoretically, the normal and tangential stiffnesses of the contact interface govern the transmission/reflection coefficients and could be used as parameters to characterize the contact condition. However, composites weak and incomplete interfaces, formed by rough surfaces in partial contact, can behave in a highly nonlinear behavior also when they are excited under free vibrations. In particular, it has been demonstrated that the amplitude of the second harmonic is a relevant index of the contact stiffness, showing that the nonlinear response is strongly influenced by the nominal contact pressure applied to the boundaries. This paper presents an experimental study aimed at developing an integrity index capable of assessing the stiffness of the contact interface between composite structures when excited by free vibration or under controlled acoustic excitation.

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that waves propagating through contact interface between solid bodies are particularly sensitive to the contact conditions such as the contact pressure and the true area of contact, and they are used as an experimental tool in contact mechanics and adhesion technology. This sensitivity can be related to the fact that the load at the contact is supported by surface asperities; increasing the nominal load applied at the boundary even more asperities are crushed and the portion of surface in contact increase. Due to the change of the contact asperity configuration with varying

nominal contact force, the mechanical response of the contact interface involves certain nonlinear behavior. These non-linearities mean that second or higher order harmonics appear as soon as a wave interacts with the surfaces [1,2,3]. This phenomenon has been investigated by adopting different techniques involving harmonic generation study [4,5], or energy transfer between the surfaces in contact by using piezoelectric transducers [6,7,8,9]. The dynamics description of moving surfaces that are in contact with each other is important in a number of different scientific and engineering applications. In previous studies it has been shown that vibration varies the contact area, modulating the phase and amplitude of higher frequency probing wave passing through the interface. In a specific case [11] the modulation effect has been observed experimentally for various materials with various types of contact-type defects; these results have then been used for developing an innovative nondestructive technique called Vibro-Acoustic Modulation Technique. In other studies has been demonstrated by simulation experiments that there is a threshold non-linear distortion due to 'clapping' and 'kissing' mechanisms, multiple bifurcations and chaos development for contact vibrations; in other studies on the Hertzian contact, the non-linearity was shown to increase with the decrease in contact load and ultrasonic waves propagating on contact interfaces exhibited extremely efficient non-linear properties, unconventional higher harmonics ratio and non-linear waveform distortion [12]. These acoustic/vibration NDE techniques reveals to be particularly reliable to predict the safety of a composite material state decided by the quality of its bonded interfaces, in fact the weakly bonded region is the possible initiation of crack propagation. In [13] the investigation using longitudinal acoustic wave was adopted as a different method to develop a contact acoustic non linearity parameter able to describe the bonding state. It has also been noticed that nonlinearities of non perfect contact interfaces are deeply affected by the hysteresis phenomenon during a loading-unloading cycle [14]; it is shown that after a first passing from the elastic to the elastoplastic contact mode, the higher harmonic amplitudes decrease more than one order of magnitude. Moreover, it was observed that under specific loading histories, the interface between smooth surfaces generates higher elastoplastic hysteresis in the interfacial stiffness, and the acoustic nonlinearity, due to the fact that when plastic flow in the contacting asperities is significant, is insensitive to the asperity peak distribution. In addition to this phenomenon, a dynamic hysteresis behavior depending on the interaction force on the interface was found by adopting a system described as a forced relaxator instead of a forced oscillator as commonly used [15]. A different way of investigation was followed by Lavrentyev and Rokhlin [16] who developed a method giving an idea of the quality of the interfacial contact by studying the effect of the contact pressure not only on the interfacial stiffness but also on the spectral shift on higher frequency. In [7,8,17] the authors monitored the health of bolted joints by analysing the energy transmitted and reflected from the contact surface using a piezoelectric transducer networks. In particular, in order to study the loosening state of a thermal protection panel joints, a washer was developed with an embedded piezoelectric element used as an actuator to generate the propagating waves as well as a sensor to receive the diagnostic waves. Then, a similar system of pitch-catch sensor network was introduced to detect cracks and debonds in metallic and composite structure which can be potentially implemented into airframe structures, in order to give also a possible damage index used to characterize the damage and know the location [6]. Structural health monitoring systems are employed in many different cases and they are suitable in different work environment from the civil to the aerospace engineering

field as a method to easily and cheaply detect the health of a structure simply analyzing the nonlinear effect or the energy response effect due to the different possible damage of structures, especially joints. Until now the techniques adopted are mainly based on the assumption of an induced acoustic vibration, but this is not always possible, not in every structure especially large scale systems, and there is the need to understand if a damage index could be developed by studying the natural free vibrations of a structure and studying the effect of different damage scenarios on these responses. Previous studies about cracks responses to vibration [4,5] have shown that an imperfection in a vibrating structure produces non-linearities visible on the frequency response as harmonics of the fundamental frequency; in this specific case the superficial roughness of the surfaces in contact at the boundary is treated as an imperfection, which generates non-linearity due to the clapping produced between the clamp and the beam surface. As already demonstrated by [4], this non-linearity produces harmonics, and it has been noticed in particular that the ratio between the amplitudes of the second harmonic and the fundamental can be strictly related to the nominal force applied at the boundary. The aim of this job is to develop a theoretical model of the nonlinear interface stiffness where the stiffness property of the contact interface was described as a function of the nominal contact pressure. It is so clear that the NDE techniques of structural health monitoring are employed in many different cases and they are suitable in different work environment from the civil to the aerospace engineering field as a method to easily and cheaply detect the health of a structure simply analyzing the nonlinear effect or the energy response effect due to the different possible damage of structures, especially joints. To reduce cost, increase availability, and maintain safety of current and future air vehicle systems, emphasis has been placed on the development of Integrated Systems Health Management (ISHM) techniques; in an imminent future an extensive use of composite materials is expected and, to improve their reliability, the composite structures also may include embedded systems able to monitor their health. Applications for innovative air vehicle structures offer the possibility to consider any sort of structural health monitoring in the design process, rather than having to retrofit a SHM system to an existing structure reducing sensitively the monitoring costs and giving an everyday possibility of structural check. Until now the techniques adopted are mainly based on the assumption of an induced acoustic vibration, but this is not always possible, not in every structure especially large scale systems, and there is the need to understand if a damage index could be developed by studying the natural free vibrations of a structure and studying the effect of different damage scenarios on these responses. Previous studies about cracks responses to vibration [4,5] have shown that an imperfection in a vibrating structure produces non-linearities visible on the frequency response as harmonics of the fundamental frequency; in this specific case the superficial roughness of the surfaces in contact at the boundary is treated as an imperfection, which generates non-linearity due to the clapping produced between the clamp and the beam surface. As already demonstrated by [4], this non-linearity produces harmonics, and it has been noticed in particular that the ratio between the amplitudes of the second harmonic and the fundamental can be strictly related to the nominal force applied at the boundary.

The aim of this job is to develop a technique to detect the nonlinear interface stiffness in composite beams as a function of the nominal contact pressure (Figure 1).

Figure 1 (a) Picture of the composite beam, (b) Accelerometer close to the contact

EXPERIMENTS

In order to reproduce a non-perfect contact configuration a specific system has been adopted; this system, depicted in Figure 2, is composed by a main structure and a specimen base; the main structure consists in a cylindrical actuator connected to four springs and moved by a screw. Since the stiffness of the springs is known, it is possible to extract the force applied by the actuator on the specimen, simply measuring the relative displacement between a fixed plate of the system and that one following the actuator motion. This force does not remain linear decreasing the distance between the plates, and the trend has been represented in Figure 3. The two plates and the beam contact that has to be analyzed are positioned in line with the actuator (Figure 1), and by screwing and unscrewing the punch are able to transfer different loads to the contact in order to reproduce different contact levels between the plates and the specimen; A similar mechanism has been used in [7], in fact it is a simple way to reproduce the effect of different torque forces applied on a joint. Considering a bolted joint, the torque applied at the bolt is directly connected to the nominal force applied on the contact surface by using a well know formula.

Figure 2 System used to reproduce the clamping force at the contact

The experiment aims to measure the out of plane acceleration of the free vibrating bar, in order to detect the amount of non-linearity coming out from different nominal load configurations. The piezoelectric accelerometer was positioned just 5mm far from the contact field, so that to be able to capture the amount of non-linearity generated by the non-perfect contact clapping; as a matter of fact, that position of the accelerometer was chosen to avoid accidentally contact between the instrument and the plate sustaining the beam, and at the same time to optimize the measurement of the second harmonic amplitude, knowing that due to the material damping it decreases moving away from the source.

Figure 3 Force Applied as a function of the plate displacement

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The first result obtained is that by increasing the force applied at the contact, independently to the second harmonic trend, a rise of the nominal amplitude connected to the first natural frequency is noted; this is physically justified by the fact that, because of the heightening of the nominal applied load at the boundary, the stiffness of the contact increased, with an increase of the out of plane beam acceleration amplitude. This phenomenon is shown in Figure 4 where two different frequency responses are plotted by varying the nominal load applied at the boundary. It is curious to notice how this trend slightly approaches to an asymptotic value reached at sometime in the raise of nominal load, as depicted in Figure 5.

This can be explained by the fact that from a certain load onward, the maximum stiffness of the contact is reached and every different change can be noticed only by a the decrease of second harmonic amplitude.

Figure 4 Frequency Response relative to the Fundamental Frequency Amplitude at two different Nominal Force Applied at the Boundary

This means that an increase of the nominal load cause a decrease of the superficial asperities and so a drop of the non-linearity due to clapping. This particular response can be appreciated by studying the behavior of the second harmonic amplitude as a function of the increasing the nominal load. In particular, by analyzing the trend of the second harmonic amplitude by varying the applied load in Figure 6 , it can be noticed that the main result of increasing load is the drop of the second harmonic amplitude, that could be explained by the crushing of the superficial asperities of the contact and the consecutive increase of contact surface reducing the clapping phenomena. In both case the scattered experimental results are well fitted with power-law curves shown as analytical trend in Figure 6.

Figure 5 Fundamental Frequency Acceleration vs Nominal Force Applied at the Boundary

Figure 6 Second Harmonic Acceleration Amplitude Trend vs Nominal Force Applied at the Boundary

Figure 7 Trend of the Ratio Index vs Nominal Force Applied at the Constraint

The effect of increasing clamping force on the ratio of second harmonic amplitude and fundamental amplitude is a power-law curve that decreases as shown in Figure 7. The

effect of increasing clamping force on the ratio of second harmonic amplitude and fundamental amplitude is a power-law decrease. The value of this ratio is an index able to predict the amount of non-linearity of the contact, and the fact that this ratio decrease increasing the nominal load implies that this can be taken as a parameter to measure the loosening state of the contact; in fact a low value of this parameter means that the strength of the contact is high enough to minimize non-linear phenomena, reflecting a low amount of contact loosening.

CONCLUSIONS

Experiments on a free vibrating composite cantilevered beam were performed in order to find out an index capable to give us an idea of the loosening grade of the joint tested. It has been demonstrated that the ratio between the second harmonic amplitude and the fundamental frequency amplitude is a reliable parameter from which the information about the amount of non-linearity connected to the contact can be extracted; moreover it is resulted that these non-linearities, due to the clapping of the contact surfaces, are a clear index of the loosening grade of the joint.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Kawashima K., Nawa K., Hattori Y., Detection of Higher Harmonics With Large Amplitude Ultrasonics. 1999, Japan Society of Non-Destructive Testing.
2. Thompson R. B., Back O., Thompson O. D., Higher Harmonics of Finite Amplitude Ultrasonic Waves in Solids s.l. : J. Acoust. Soc. Am, 1976, Vol. 59.
3. S.I. Rokhlin, M. Hefets, M. Rosen. An Ultrasonic interface-wave method for predicting the strength of adhesive bonds., 4, s.l. : J. Appl. Phys., 1981, Vol. 52.
4. S. Biwa, S. Nakajima, N. Ohno., On the Acoustic Nonlinearity of Solid-Solid Contact With Pressure-Dependent Interface Stiffness, s.l. : Journal of Applied Mechanics, 2004, Vol. 71.
5. K. Kawashima, M. Murase, R. Yamada, M. Matsushima, M. Uematsu, F. Fujita., Nonlinear Ultrasonic imaging of imperfectly bonded interfaces, s.l. : Elsevier, June 2, 2006, Ultrasonics.
6. J. B. Ihn, F. K. Chang., Pitch-catch Active Sensing Methods in Structural Health Monitoring for Aircraft Structures, s.l. : SAGE, 2008, Structural Health Monitoring, Vol. 7(1).
7. J. Yang, F. K. Chang., Detection of bolt loosening in C-C composite thermal protection panels: I. Diagnostic principle, s.l. : Institute of Physics, 2006, Smart Material and Structures , Vol. 15, pp. 581-590.
8. J. Yang, F. K. Chang, M. M. Derriso., Design of a Hierarchical Health Monitoring System for Detection of Multilevel Damage in Bolted Thermal Protection Panels: A Preliminary Study, s.l. : SAGE, 2003, Structural Health Monitoring, Vol. 2(2).
9. J. Esteban, C. A. Rogers., Energy dissipation through joints: theory and experiments, s.l. : Elsevier, 1999, Computers & Structures, Vol. 75, pp. 347-359.

10. Drinkwater et. al, A Study of Interaction Between Ultrasound and a Partially Contacting Solid-Solid Interface, 1955, s.l. : Proc. R. Soc., 1996, Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences, Vol. 452.
11. D. Donskoy, A. Sutin, A. Ekimov., Nonlinear acoustic interaction on contact interfaces and its use for nondestructive testing, 4, s.l. : Elsevier, NDT and E International, Vol. 34.
12. Yu, Solodov I., Ultrasonics of non-linear contacts: propagation, reflection and NDE-applications, 1-5, s.l. : Elsevier, 1998, Ultrasonics, Vol. 36.
13. Jian-jun Chen, De Zhang, Yi-wei Mao., Contact acoustic nonlinearity phenomena caused by the acoustic wave propagating in composite material, s.l. : IEEE, 2008, Piezoelectricity, Acoustic Waves, and Device Applications.
14. Jin-Yeon Kim, Arturo Baltazar, Jong Wan Hu, Stan I. Rokhlin., Hysteretic linear and nonlinear acoustic responses from pressed interfaces, 21, s.l. : Elsevier, 2006, International journal of solids and structures, Vol. 43.
15. V. Gusev, B. Castagnede, A. Moussatov., Hysteresis in response of nonlinear bistable interface to continuously varying acoustic loading, 8, s.l. : Elsevier, 2003, Ultrasonics, Vol. 41.
16. A.I. Lavrentyev, S.I. Rokhlin. Ultrasonic spectroscopy of imperfect contact interfaces between a layer and two solids, 2, s.l. : AIP, 1998, The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America, Vol. 103.
17. J. Yang, F.K. Chang., Verification of a built-in health monitoring system for bolted thermal protection panels, s.l. : SPIE, 2005, SHM for Composite Material, Vol. 5765.